

CAST-IN HARDFACING COMPOSITE

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Abstract

Tungsten carbide and chromium ferroalloy particles in binderless state were put on the vacuum sealed mould surface, and wear resistant surface was formed by pouring high temperature liquid steel into cavity of the mould. Surface layer was strengthened when tungsten carbide and chromium ferroalloy particles were matched at suitable volume ratio. Higher surface hardness HRC 65-69 and more toughness have been obtained by this composite material. Three-body abrasion and pin-on-disc tests were carried out. The wear resistance increases with increasing the size and the volume percentage of tungsten carbide particles. Microstructures of specimens were observed by SEM. Around WC particle surfaces some diffusion shells exist due to some degree of reaction between WC particles and matrix. It was found that strengthened martensitic matrix alloyed by tungsten and chromium supports tungsten carbide particles as well as reformed carbides (M_6C , M_7C_3) strongly. Finally, the WC particles stood in relief on the surface, the cutting and ploughing effects of abrasives on surface were controlled and reduced. Therefore WC particles contributes more effectively to wear resistance.

KEYWORDS: Particulate composite; Metallic matrix; Interface; Wear; Manufacturing.

1. INTRODUCTION

As well known, a huge amount of materials are worn down in industries every year, although some failures of machine parts occur only due to their surface dimensions worn out of tolerance. Recently there is currently of interest in the material

engineering through modifying the surface of materials by means of various processes. In order to reduce material consumption, the composite material fabricated by casting method is a more suitable one because it is not only simple and less cost, but also takes more technical and economical advantages, i.e., thickness and performance of surface layer may be designed in a wide range comfortably. It is traditional that such surface layer may be formed by coating the slurries or pastes containing wear resistant particles and liquid binders on the mold surface (1). In practice, it may be trouble that the blowhole and slag inclusion are hardly diminished so that lowers the wear resistance and the performance of the materials. In this paper, loose abrasive resistant particles, such as WC and high chromium ferroalloy particles were put on the surface of vacuum sealed mold, the particles were sucked and localized on the surface by vacuum force. When liquid steel was poured, a wear resistant surface layer was formed (2). Because this process purifies the interfaces and improves the diffusion conditions of the interacting materials, the firmly coherent effect on the particulate-matrix interfaces may be obtained. By evidence, the composite materials reinforced by WC particles manufactured by this method contributed more effectively to the wear resistance.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORKS

2.1 Specimens Specimens were cast by vacuum sealed molding process. The dimension of specimen was 140x70x(10-30)mm. When the plastic film was covered on the pattern, the wear resistant particles were put on the film where abrasive wear resistance was necessary, then silica sand was filled, finally another film was covered on the top side of flask. The mold was formed while the air inside flasks were sucked out. Unbounded particles were firmly held in place (shown in Figure 1). After high temperature liquid steel was poured into the cavity of mould, steel casting with wear resistant surface layer was finished. Vacuum inside sand mold was 160-260 Torr.

2.2 Materials The base material used in experiments was carbon steel containing 0.45% C . Pouring temperature of steel was 1550-1600°C. Wear resistant particles were WC and high chromium ferroalloy.

The volume ratio of WC and chromium ferroalloy was 4:1.

The grain size of particles is listed in Table 1.

FIGURE 1. Mould surface with wear resistant particles
 1. plastic film; 2. cavity;
 3. WC and Cr ferroalloy particles

TABLE 1 GRAIN SIZE OF WEAR RESISTANT PARTICLES

No. of specimens	Grain size of particles (mesh)	
	WC	Cr ferroalloy
S1	140/200	140/200
S2	100/140	100/140
S3	80/100	100/140
S4	70/80	70/100
S5	60/70	70/100
S6	28/40	50/70
S7	18/28	30/50

2.3 Hardness of Specimens Hardness of surface layer is one of the more important properties of wear abrasion resistant materials. Here, the Rockwell hardness was measured in as-cast and heat-treated conditions, shown in Figure 2.

Hardness of surface layer in as-cast condition ranges from HRC 54.2 to HRC 68.1, and in heat-treated condition from HRC 65.6 to HRC 69.2. Heat treatment makes the hardness more higher as compared with that in as-cast condition.

3. MICROSTRUCTURES

Microstructures of cast-in hard surface provided by this process were observed under optical microscope and SEM. The infiltrated steel base metal and dissolved chromium ferroalloy as well as WC particles formed the surface layer uniformly. Solidification of base metal and surface layer began from their interface, and the former solidified earlier than the latter.

Figure 3 shows the microstructure of steel base- surface layer

interface. Base steel infiltrated into surface layer, tungsten carbide and chromium in surface layer diffused into base metal. Evidently, metallurgical coherence resulted and no defects were observed.

WC particles were dissolved somewhat around their surfaces and complex diffusion shells around the WC particles were formed.

The photographs are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

3.1 As-Cast Condition

After pouring, the carbon contained in WC and high Cr ferroalloy diffused into infiltrated base

steel, simultaneously, the partially dissolved tungsten and chromium diffused into metal matrix rapidly, this phenomenon resulted the W content in metal matrix up to about 20%. This effect was confirmed by X-ray energy dispersive analysis. And the finer the WC particles, the more dissolved in its matrix. Because the concentration of W and Cr was high in metal matrix

FIGURE 2 Hardness of surface layer
 [White bar] as-cast condition
 [Hatched bar] heat-treated condition

FIGURE 3 Steel-surface layer interface of S5
 left-steel base
 right- surface layer

FIGURE 4 Surface layer of S3

FIGURE 5. SEM photograph of diffusion shell around WC particle surface (No. S3)

of surface layer, the stability of austenite was so high that its transformation could not occur. If any, just only a small amount of martensite could be formed.

3.2 Heat-treated Condition Specimens were heated to 970°C for 2 hrs., then air quenched. Microstructure of surface layer became martensite. W as well as Cr in matrix entered into the secondary carbides in dispersed state. And polygonal carbides were formed. Concentration of the polygonal carbide (Figure 6) was measured by X-ray energy dispersive analysis. It contains W about 60% and more. Microhardness of polygonal carbides is HV 1580-2027. Hardness of matrix is HV 711-1013.

FIGURE 6. Surface layer of S3 WC particles, polygonal carbides and martensitic matrix.

4. ABRASION TESTS

4.1 Two-body Abrasion Test Two-body (pin-on-disc) abrasion test was carried out on a pin-on-disc abrasion tester (ML-10)

with Al 203 sheets. Diameter of specimen was 4 mm. Each sample was under normal pressure of 2.4 MPa. Because this hard surface is higher wear resistant, the weight loss after each run test is quite small. So every specimen is subjected to wear test twice with a total test stroke of 18.4 m. The results are shown in Figure 7.

FIGURE 7. Results of pin-on-disc abrasion test
 \circ as-cast condition
 Δ heat-treated condition

4.2 Three-body Abrasion Test In order to study the influence of different pressure on the wear resistance of various specimens three-body abrasion was investigated by a rebuilt abrasion wear tester with silica sand (70/140 mesh). Each specimen was tested under normal pressure of 0.05 MPa, 0.07 MPa and 0.09 MPa separately. At the same time, specimens rotated on a circle rail with linear speed of 16.4 m/min. Each run lasted 30 min. The average value of 5 runs of the wear resistance was adopted. The wear resistance of each specimen was compared with that of low C steel specimen (0.20% C, normalized). The wear test data of hard surface layer are given in Table 2.

5. DISCUSSION

1. The microstructure of the matrix in surface layer transformed into martensite by heat treatment so that its own wear resistance increased. Hence the alloyed carbides as well as WC particles were in the situation where they were firmly supported by the matrix. During two-body abrasion test, WC particles in surface layer could only be scratched rather than cut efficiently by alumina abrasives, because H_m/H_a was about 1.5 which made the alumina abrasive as a soft abrasive

TABLE 2 RESULTS OF THREE-BODY ABRASION TEST

No. of specimens	Mean size of WC μm	Vol. % of WC	Wear resistance*		
			0.05 MPa	0.07MPa	0.09 MPa
S1	90	—	2.61	—	—
S2	127	32.0	2.74	—	—
S3	163	35.7	3.07	—	—
S4	194	38.8	3.30	—	—
S5	230	39.8	5.42	5.65	6.46
S6	504	49.5	8.88	13.88	15.64
S7	795	52.3	9.53	14.40	17.45
W1	—	—	1.24	—	—
high Cr cast iron	—	—	1.41	1.31	1.27

* Wear resistance= wt. loss of 0.2% C steel/ wt. loss of specimen

(3), although the hardness of alumina abrasive is HV 1800-2000. Consequently, WC particles stood in relief of the surface and contributed more efficiently to the wear resistance. Only slightly scratched lines on the abraded surface appeared.

2. Figure 8 shows the microstructure of specimen S7 abraded 3.5 hrs. continuously in three-body abrasion test. At the beginning, the abrasives indented the soft matrix and the soft matrix was preferentially abraded by rolling and cutting of the abrasives and removed gradually. Till the

FIGURE 8. SEM of S7 surface (air quenched) subjected abrading 3.5 hrs long in three-body abrasion test

depth removed was deeper than the abrasive size, the preferentially cutting effect was reduced. Then the WC particle individually stood in relief of the surface layer and was abraded smoothly. Simultaneously, the projecting of WC particles restricted the indentation of the abrasives so that wear resistance increased steeply.

3. Higher stress three-body abrasion tests were performed. Results (Table 2) show that wear resistance of the surface layer of specimens S5, S6 and S7 which contained coarse WC particles increased with abrading pressure (0.05, 0.07 and 0.09 MPa) from 5.42, 8.88 and 9.53 to 6.46, 15.64 and 17.54 respectively. It illustrates that materials fabricated by this method were much more preferable for higher stress abrasion conditions and about 3-10 times higher than that of high chromium cast iron.
4. The wear resistance of specimens also increases with increasing volume percentage of WC particles (Table 2), wear resistance increases dramatically while volume percentage of WC above 40%.
5. As listed in Table 2, the wear resistance of specimens which consisted with WC and chromium ferroalloy particles were higher than that of specimen W1 which no chromium ferroalloy contained as its binder metal.
6. It is of interest to note that the hardness of alloyed polygonal carbide was much higher than that of abrasives (silica and alumina grains), so that they could not be preferentially cut by abrasives. Simultaneously, they restricted the ploughing and cutting on matrix due to decreased space of matrix between carbides.

6. CONCLUSIONS

1. The complex diffusion shells around WC particle-matrix interfaces were formed due to the binder metal protecting WC particles from dissolving.
2. The particulate-matrix interfaces formed by high chromium ferroalloy as a binder metal for WC particles contributed more effectively to the wear resistance of surface layer.
3. Wear resistance increases dramatically when volume percentage of WC particles in surface layer is above 40%.

4. Coarser WC particles perform its important function to wear resistance than the finer and the function is enhanced by the stronger support provided by alloyed martensitic matrix.
5. Surface layer is more preferable for higher stress three-body abrasion condition.

7. REFERENCES

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